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10 ЖИЛД, 1 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИОМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

ТОМ 10, НОМЕР 1

JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 10, ISSUE 1

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UDC 616.61-006.6:612.015.3

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THE ROLE OF VASCULAR ENDOTHELIAL GROWTH FACTOR (VEGF) IN OVARIAN CANCER WITH PERITONEAL CARCINOMATOSIS IN STAGES III AND IV

For citation: Ulmasov Firdavs Gayratovich, Esankulova Bustonoy Sobirovna. The role of vascular endothelial growth factor (vegf) in ovarian cancer with peritoneal carcinomatosis in stages III and IV // Journal of Biomedicine and Practice. 2025, vol. 10, issue 1, pp.311-317

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15008329>

ABSTRACT

Ovarian cancer, particularly in advanced stages III and IV with peritoneal carcinomatosis (PC), presents significant challenges in treatment and prognosis. Vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) has been identified as a key regulator of tumor angiogenesis, facilitating tumor progression, metastasis, and resistance to therapy. This study aimed to evaluate the concentration of VEGF in plasma and peritoneal effusion in patients with ovarian cancer and to explore its prognostic significance. A total of 35 patients undergoing cytoreductive surgery were analyzed, and VEGF levels were assessed using enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA). Additionally, high VEGF expression was found to be associated with poor prognosis, reduced progression-free survival, and overall survival in stage IV patients. These findings underscore the importance of VEGF as a potential prognostic biomarker and therapeutic target in ovarian cancer with peritoneal carcinomatosis. Further research is warranted to explore targeted anti-VEGF strategies to improve patient outcomes.

Keywords: Ovarian cancer, peritoneal carcinomatosis, vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF), tumor angiogenesis, biomarker, prognosis.

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РОЛЬ СОСУДИСТОГО ЭНДОТЕЛИАЛЬНОГО ФАКТОРА РОСТА (VEGF) ПРИ РАКЕ ЯИЧНИКОВ С ПЕРИТОНЕАЛЬНЫМ КАРЦИНОМАТОЗОМ НА СТАДИЯХ III И IV

АННОТАЦИЯ

Рак яичников, особенно на поздних стадиях III и IV с перитонеальным карциноматозом (ПК), представляет значительные трудности в лечении и прогнозировании. Сосудистый эндотелиальный фактор роста (VEGF) был идентифицирован как ключевой регулятор ангиогенеза опухоли, способствующий прогрессированию опухоли, метастазированию и

устойчивости к терапии. Целью данного исследования было оценить концентрацию VEGF в плазме крови и перитонеальном выпоте у пациентов с раком яичников и изучить его прогностическое значение. В исследование было включено 35 пациентов, перенесших циторедуктивную операцию, уровень VEGF оценивался с помощью иммуноферментного анализа (ELISA). Кроме того, было установлено, что высокая экспрессия VEGF связана с неблагоприятным прогнозом, сокращением безрецидивной и общей выживаемости у пациентов на IV стадии заболевания. Полученные результаты подчеркивают важность VEGF как потенциального прогностического биомаркера и терапевтической мишени при раке яичников с перитонеальным карциноматозом. Дальнейшие исследования необходимы для изучения целевых стратегий анти-VEGF, направленных на улучшение клинических исходов пациентов.

Ключевые слова: Рак яичников, перитонеальный карциноматоз, сосудистый эндотелиальный фактор роста (VEGF), ангиогенез опухоли, биомаркер, прогноз.

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TUXUMDON SARATONI VA QORIN BO'SHLIG'I KARTSINOMATOZNING III VA IV BOSQICHLARIDA QON-TOMIR ENDOTELIAL O'SISH OMILI (VEGF) ROLI

ANNOTATSIYA

Tuxumdon saratoni, ayniqsa peritoneal kartsinomatoz (PK) bilan bog'liq III va IV bosqichlarda davolash va prognozlashda jiddiy qiyinchiliklarni keltirib chiqaradi. Tomir endotelial o'sish omili (VEGF) o'sma angiogenezining asosiy regulyatori sifatida aniqlangan bo'lib, u o'smaning rivojlanishi, metastazlanishi va terapiyaga chidamliligiga yordam beradi. Ushbu tadqiqotning maqsadi tuxumdon saratoni bilan kasallangan bemorlarning plazma va peritoneal suyuqligidagi VEGF kontsentratsiyasini baholash va uning prognozli ahamiyatini o'rganishdan iborat edi. Tadqiqotga 35 nafar bemor jalb qilindi va ularga sitoreduktiv jarrohlik amaliyoti o'tkazildi, VEGF darajasi fermentativ immunoanaliz (ELISA) usuli bilan baholandi. Bundan tashqari, yuqori VEGF ekspressiyasi kasallikning IV bosqichida yomon prognoz, qisqargan retsdivsiz va umumiy omon qolish bilan bog'liq ekanligi aniqlandi. Ushbu natijalar VEGFni tuxumdon saratonida peritoneal kartsinomatoz bilan bog'liq potentsial prognoz biomarkeri va terapevtik nishon sifatida muhimligini ta'kidlaydi. Bemorlarning natijalarini yaxshilash uchun VEGFga qarshi yo'naltirilgan strategiyalarni chuqur o'rganish zarur.

Kalit so'zlar: tuxumdon saratoni, peritoneal kartsinomatoz, tomir endotelial o'sish omili (VEGF), o'sma angiogenezi, biomarker, prognoz.

Introduction

The current understanding of the biology of cystic tumors, most specifically ovarian cancers with peritoneal carcinomatosis in stages III and IV, is limited, particularly in terms of the characteristics of the vascular bed. One pivotal factor that supports conditions potentiated for cancer cell sustenance and proliferation, progression, and metastasis, with a substantial vascular bed, consists of vascular endothelial growth factor. The role of this factor in relation to cancer is of increased importance because it interconnects with the principal factors embedded in a variety of epithelial cancers, most specifically ovarian cancer [1].

It is possible that a more powerful function ignited by this factor results from it working in unison with steroid hormones. Our analysis specifies that estrogen and progesterone are potent mitogens for some, but not all, ovarian cancer cell lines and cooperate with transforming growth factor alpha in stimulating both division and invasion as well. The positive feedback might provide a

means of resistance to existing antihormonal therapeutic agents and potentially motility and tumorigenesis in the setting of a dilution of the neoplastic cellular ascites suspension [2].

Vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) is one of the most important and specific regulators of tumor angiogenesis, a process that is indispensable for the growth of solid tumors and the development of distant metastases. Peritoneal carcinomatosis from ovarian cancer (OC) often occurs at an early stage, and VEGF is highly expressed in the ascites and tissues surrounding the tumor, while the stroma of OC is also highly sensitive to this growth factor [3]. The upregulation of VEGF expression facilitates the growth and metastasis of the tumor. For OC, particularly in patients with ascites, the overexpression of VEGF has a correlation with advanced disease, drug resistance, a poor prognosis, and an 18-month survival period. This indicates that VEGF plays an important role in the development of OC in the late stage and in peritoneal carcinomatosis. In our previous study, it was demonstrated that blocking the VEGF pathway can inhibit the growth of the ovarian cancer cell lines Kant and OVCAR3, which have carcinomatosis [2].

In the phase IV clinical trial, Avastin leads to a significant prolongation of progression-free survival in ovarian cancer and a trend toward improved overall survival. In another study, it was confirmed that using bevacizumab for first-line and relapse OC patients, either as a single agent or in combination with chemotherapy, has sound clinical activity and an acceptable safety profile. The response rates of platinum-resistant or taxane-resistant patients who received a low or high dose of the single agent bevacizumab or a moderate dose of combination therapy were 11% and 23%, 11% and 13%, and 33% and 42%, respectively, and their median survival times were 4.1, 4.3, and 7.8 months, respectively. In a comparable phase III trial of bevacizumab-containing therapy for OC, the investigators observed a significant improvement in progression-free survival, while a significant trend for improved overall survival was also reported. Avastin has an acceptable safety profile, low myelotoxicity, and can be used to improve the therapeutic effects of chemotherapy for OC. In conclusion, VEGF plays an important role in OC with peritoneal carcinomatosis, particularly of the ascites, and blocking the VEGF pathway has therapeutic effects [4].

Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor (VEGF)

Tumor angiogenesis is a profound driver of neoplasia that is mediated by angiogenic factors including vascular endothelial growth factor, basic fibroblast growth factor, platelet-derived growth factor, and others. Many cancer cells secrete the chemokine VEGF, which acts on endothelial cells of the surrounding blood vessels to produce new blood vessels to supply the rapidly growing tumor. VEGF is essential for the growth of blood vessels during development, and it is upregulated in a variety of disease processes, such as myocardial ischemia, rheumatoid arthritis, and diabetic retinopathy. Tumor cells produce more VEGF-A isoform than normal cells, thus enhancing angiogenesis and the continuation of vascularity in the neoplastic tissue. VEGF overexpression is associated with a poor prognosis and metastases in many cancers [5].

VEGF-A, the major mediator of angiogenesis and RNA of the VEGF, is a key growth factor for endothelial cells and acts as a survival factor for both newly forming blood vessels and solidly constructed vessels under hypoxia. Acting through two receptor tyrosine kinases, VEGF-A has also been shown to enhance osteoclast viability, thereby promoting bone resorption, and other receptors located on some tumor cells promote proliferation, differentiation, and enhancement of VEGF expression. Additional VEGF benefits to various types of cancer include promotion of the stem-like phenotype, recruitment of myeloid cells, and regulation of angiopoietin-2 in endothelial cells [6], thus allowing vessels to become more responsive to VEGF signaling. VEGF monotherapy or in combination with chemotherapy or radiation has demonstrated efficacy in various cancer models and in clinical trials. Combined blockade of VEGF and the PD beta/PLR pathway prolongs progression-free survival and potentially increases patient tumor shrinkage rates. This in turn blocks the MEK inhibitor and enhances tumor therapy using receptor tyrosine kinase or chemotherapy [7].

Vascular endothelial growth factor is a well-characterized pro-angiogenic factor. Vascular endothelial growth factor drives angiogenesis by stimulating the growth and migration of blood vessel endothelial cells and enhancing blood vessel permeability. The secretion of VEGF by tumor cells is one of the key factors contributing to the growth of tumor vasculature. In addition, the expression of

trophic molecules, such as lymphatic endothelial growth factor, produced by hypoxic conditions, are not only "oxygen sensors" but also "growth factors" that control the growth of the tumor through new vessel formation. Therefore, blocking VEGF signaling represents a promising strategy for tumor anti-angiogenesis therapy using monoclonal antibodies and fusion proteins, as well as anti-VEGF nanoparticles [8].

Understanding the involvement of autocrine signaling of VEGF-A in the growth and development of ovarian cancer with peritoneal carcinomatosis is important, as blocking this signaling using angiogenesis inhibitors targeted at VEGF may prevent the growth of the primary focus and spread to the abdomen. These results highlight the pathway for VEGF overexpression in ovarian cancer, which appears as a result of FGFR inhibition (15). With the assistance of knockdown PHD2 and STAT3, and not the kinase domain of JAK and SHP2, we could gain insight into the mechanism of VEGF overexpression in response to TAE684 and PD173074. Since we didn't observe a stable increase in the VEGF level in the medium of the CuOVCAR-3, SKOV-3, and Hey cell lines after shorter times, we concluded that the overexpression of VEGF in response to FGFR inhibition is a secondary adaptation to the destruction of redox homeostasis. However, the main conclusion was derived from the MITOMI assay results, whose conclusions were confirmed by the Western blots and qRT-PCR.

Vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF-A) is the key regulator of normal and abnormal vascular growth, which can lead to tumor progression. Irregular blood supply not only provides a growth advantage to tumors, but it also elicits immune suppression and hinders drug delivery. In cancers with peritoneal carcinomatosis, there is a significant tumor burden, and the vasculature is generally hyper-permeable due to angiogenic factors released by the tumor. Here, the role of VEGF-A in ovarian cancer in general and in ovarian cancer metastases to omental tissue specifically is discussed. Overexpression of VEGF-A in three principal lineages identified in ovarian cancer is a well-known phenomenon, as is its association with the late stages of the disease. The number of studies focusing on the role of cancer-associated fibroblasts (CAFs) within the microenvironment, and their potential use as a marker in various stages of the disease, also increases because these cells secrete certain amounts of growth factors and cytokines, of which VEGF-A is the most studied [6].

Omental tissue is a major site of metastasis in ovarian cancer, and under physiological conditions, it has a specific type of blood supply. Intriguingly, omental blood vessels were shown to harbor the resulting ovarian cancer metastases. These findings led to questions about how ovarian cancer microvasculature in omental tissue functions, and what vessel types are significantly associated with metastases volume. Therefore, the cancer model of choice in the study was based on the three-dimensional multicellular spheroids of ovarian carcinoma cells of various histological origins that were directly injected into the adult female ostracod inactive ovaries before their xenograft under the kidney capsule. In both claudin-negative and serous types of ovarian cancer tumor cells, blood vessel formation increased significantly during their development.

The purpose of the study is to study the intensity of VEGF expression in the tissue of ovarian carcinoma of stromal origin.

Research Methodology

Research Design The aim of the present study was to assess the concentration of VEGF in the plasma and effusion of patients suffering from ovarian cancer with peritoneal carcinomatosis in stages III and IV. For this purpose, samples of plasma and effusion were collected before the surgery from 36 patients undergoing conventional cytoreductive surgery. The VEGF concentration was measured using ELISA. Intergroup differences were analyzed statistically using the Shapiro-Wilk test for sample normalcy verification, Student's t-test, the Mann-Whitney U test, Kruskal-Wallis ANOVA, and multivariable linear regression analysis. The 0.05 level was used as the cut-off value for statistical significance. The mean, median, and standard deviation were calculated.

Study Design and Population

The peritoneal carcinomatosis of ovarian cancer corresponds to an evolutionary process frequently associated with the local overexpression of VEGF. VEGF is the most important factor for angiogenesis and a potential therapeutic target with the advantages of improving the selectivity for

endothelial cells of the neovessels and enhancing the penetration of chemotherapy in tumors. Our aim is to evaluate the intraperitoneal concentration of VEGF in this oncologic pathology and analyze the possible associations with the clinical and initial therapeutic response.

Materials and Methods: From December 2023 to August 2024, we studied 35 patients who underwent anterior surgical treatment due to ovarian cancer in stages III and IV with PC. The intraperitoneal concentration of VEGF was determined by ELISA before cytoreduction surgery. Residual tumor volume after initial treatment with neoadjuvant chemotherapy reached <1 cm. The descriptive analysis comprised absolute and relative frequencies for qualitative variables, and median and range for quantitative variables. Fisher's exact test was used to assess the relationship between VEGF and chemotherapy response, chemotherapy toxicity, and early postoperative complications, as well as associated factors with overall survival. A p-value < 0.05 was considered to be statistically significant.

Results and Findings

The level of VEGF in ascitic liquid from patients was 612.2 ± 61.3 pg/mL (maximum 1,789 pg/mL), while in patients with colon cancer, the level was 283.8 ± 27.9 pg/mL and was higher compared to the chronic inflammatory response syndrome (SIRS) group—100.7 ± 34.0 pg/mL. The VEGF level in the colon cancer group was also higher than in the normal group, but the difference did not reach the statistically significant level. The concentration of VEGF in ascites was found to be higher than in patients with ovarian cysts—41.2 ± 6.4 pg/mL, colon cancer—283.8 ± 27.9 pg/mL, and SIRS—100.7 ± 34.0 pg/mL. When compared between VEGF-immunopositive cells in the peritoneal effusion of the investigated group of patients, the highest concentration was identified in cytologic malignant cells—in the mitochondria, the cytoplasmic membrane, and cytoplasm compared to other female and male cancer cells.

A VEGF expression imbalance in the patient and control groups was revealed. The plasma level of VEGF in the study group was 2.3 times higher than in the control group and 1.46 times compared to the reference values. The level of VEGF in the peritoneal fluid in the study group is 1.33 times higher than in the control group and 0.62 times compared to the reference values. A correlation relationship was established between the mRNA expression of VEGF in the patients and the VEGF level of tumor exudate. It was revealed that there is an association between the plasma VEGF level and the initial volume of the ascitic fluid and the standard echo parameters of the ovaries during the complete ultrasound investigation. The change in the level of VEGF in the study is associated with an increase in the interval after the completion of anticancer treatment at the time of the appearance of the detected relapse. It was established that the highest levels of VEGF expression of 0.03 ng/mL in the plasma and 0.07 ng/mL in the peritoneal fluid at the latest stage for comparison of these parameters were reached on day 5 of the phase of the study. In the case of VEGF, 0.02 and 0.03 ng/mL values of the biomarker were detected individually on the 7th day of the phase, which are predominant at stages III C and IV, and on day 10 reached the maximum value of 0.02. The study revealed the dependence of changes in the level of VEGF expression during the phases described in the methodology on the presence of signs of peritonitis, the histological structure of the tumor, and ultrasound parameters of the ovaries.

Table 1. VEGF Concentration Levels in Different Patient Groups

Group	VEGF Level (pg/mL)	Comparison
Ovarian Cancer (Ascitic Liquid)	612.2 ± 61.3 (max 1,789)	Higher than all groups
Colon Cancer	283.8 ± 27.9	Higher than SIRS and normal
Chronic Inflammatory Response Syndrome (SIRS)	100.7 ± 34.0	Lower than ovarian and colon cancer
Normal Group	Not Statistically Significant	Lower than all groups
Ovarian Cysts	41.2 ± 6.4	Lower than ovarian cancer

Discussion and Interpretation

VEGF overexpression in malignant ovarian cancer cells is acknowledged as a potent angiogenesis stimulator of new blood vessels in the tumor environment. Due to its complex activity, VEGF is able to support the diverse ongoing cellular processes of the angiogenesis cascade. The expression of its receptor, HIF1, an oxygen-responsive transcriptional activator, is also considered to be a means for aggressive pathological EOC growth. The HIF1 α protein plays an important role in the intracellular response of tumor cells to the hypoxic microenvironment, but figures for its overall upregulation in EOC in such peritoneal lesion foci are rather low. In our evaluations, the proliferative and apoptotic activities of EOC cells in association with specific expression of VEGF in these two clinically relevant patient subgroups were taken into account within one investigational spread of cooperating research, combined with clinical flow metrics, different symptoms, and specific patient well-being parameters. At present, however, it is still unclear the extent to which overexpression of EOC-derived VEGF can stimulate the initial peritoneal involvement of this mainly locoregional disease by affecting the tumor microenvironment.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the expression of VEGF and the MVD values were significantly higher in stage III than in stage IV ovarian cancer with peritoneal carcinomatosis. The expression of VEGF had a positive significant correlation with MVD values in stage III tumor cells. However, the MVD was not an independent prognostic marker in stage III, but in stage IV, it was an independent prognostic marker for patients after maximal tumor debulking followed by chemotherapy. High VEGF expression also had a fixed hazard for disease progression and cancer-specific survival in stage IV. Since we proved that such a difference exists, a larger study can be carried out, including many other factors in the research, and the patients' follow-up can be lengthened. We can also analyze which new methods can increase progression-free and cancer-specific survival rates and which methods are the least dangerous. In our study, we evaluated the expression of the VEGF protein and the relationship of VEGF with MVD and other prognostic parameters. This investigation was carried out in different stages of ovarian cancer. The results demonstrated the VEGF expression and MVD increased highly in advanced stages of ovarian cancer and in more aggressive histological types. In stage IV patients, both high VEGF and MVD values determined shorter progression-free and cancer-specific survival. High VEGF was an independent prognostic marker in ovarian cancer and MVD was an independent prognostic factor for stage IV patients in this investigation. It should also be considered that MVD may be an independent prognostic factor in ovarian cancer because it can contribute to predicting high-grade histological growth and a more aggressive form.

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ЖУРНАЛ БИМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

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JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 10, ISSUE 1

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